

DIGITAL DISTRACTIONS BASED ON DIGITAL MARKETING WITH REFERENCE TO ODISHA

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Abstract:

Distraction is the key reasons for inefficiency in any activity or task. The choice is after realizing the effects people evolve or retain. Evolve lead to betterment where as retaining the same leads to waste of time and efforts resulting in poor focus of activity. What happens when a person is distracted? Actually the person mind shifts the activity on process to activity that tempts or alarms. This becomes a habit on practice loosing concentration on what to be done. Activity of a human can be in two parts 1. Productive and 2. Non Productive. Productive activity is one with time framed tasks and which result in revenue generation or for a useful cause. Whereas non productive activity is for entertainment or fun or like or addiction which will not or will have low impact on an individual knowledge or revenue generation process. The conclusion is that apart from the respondents who are from the age group between 47-55 the respondents from other age group felt anxious and lost due to use of digital gadgets and also female respondents believe that use of digital gadgets may lead to mood improvement. This factor has to be eradicated as this cause harm and may addict them towards continuous usage of digital gadgets in future period of time.

Key Words: Distraction, Digital Gadgets, Productivity, Mind Process, Control, Focus

Introduction:

The factors influencing distraction is increasing with gadgets on hands and watch. Olden days people where in peace without much distraction. The first ever invention which put people on stay is radio and then followed television and then came the computer followed by digital Medias. When radio was to listen to new it was optimum and timely usage. The same shifted to entertainment and where the digital era as distraction era raised. Portable music systems like walk man and head phone was the first every invention to make people listen more on entertainment during the work. Today the smart phone which handles alarm to online purchase holds the major responsibility in distraction. The messaging apps alerts cause the destruction to diversified factors like loss of productivity to serious accidents. The people with smart phone are tempted to watch or use the gadget shifting their focus from primary work to allied activity which adds fun and entertainment.

Statement of the Problem:

There are many research works stating the phycology behind distraction. Research has shown that distractions cause people to take longer to complete a task. Distractions not only just take up time; they also degrade the overall quality of people’s work. But this study portrays the usage of digital gadgets, which are the most common reasons for distraction in education and work place. The Study explains the level of distractions due to digital gadgets and explains solution to handle the digital gadget for effectiveness in work or education. This study also peels of the health related issues due to prolonged usage of digital gadgets segment wise.

Conceptual Framework:

Objectives of the Study:

- To study about the demographic variables of the respondents.
- To evaluate inability to control craving among the respondents.
- To analyze the anxious feeling and loosing stability due to usage of digital medias.
- To mood improvement due to digital factors.

Scope of the Study:

The users are most of time are in digital locked on information search, chats, social media, entertainment and fun. The is no age restriction for digital gadget usage, from kids at the age of 3 to elders at 55 are most commonly found in social media with person digital devices. The goal of the study is to it highlight the usage of digital gadgets which leads to distractions resulting in low productivity at education, work and life. And to understand the possible way for reducing it to increase the focus and better living.

Research Methodology:

- Type of Research: Descriptive research has been used analyzing the gadget usage parameter in various
- Type of Methodology Used: As the population is undefined stratified random sampling has been used towards the study.

Data Collection:

- Primary Data: The primary data is been using questionnaire method.
- Secondary Data: The secondary data has been collected from Journals, websites and Articles.
- Sample Size: The sample size for the study was 250 and the data was collected from the respondents including kids and people working in various industries.

Tools Used for the Study:

Percentage analysis, Descriptive statistics, multiple regression and One way Anova.

Limitations of the Study:

- The sample size is limited to 250 respondents.
- The study area is limited to Certain Industry
- There may be a bias towards the primary data collected from the respondents.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Demographic Variable of the Respondents

Demographic Variables	Particulars	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	73	66.40
	Female	37	33.60
	Total	110	100.00
Age	13-23 Years	32	29.10
	24-35 years	28	25.50
	36-46 Years	36	32.70
	47-55 Years	7	6.40
	Above 56 Years	7	6.40
	Total	110	100.00
Educational Qualification	SSLC/HSC Level	2	1.80
	Degree / Diploma	24	21.80
	Post Graduate	79	71.80
	Professional degree	5	4.50
	Total	110	100.00
Nature of Respondents	Student	19	17.30
	Working Class	14	12.70
	Professionals	38	34.50
	House Wife's	4	3.60
	Business Men	33	30.00
	Retired	2	1.80
	Total	110	100.00
Type of family	Joint	29	26.40
	Nuclear	81	73.60
	Total	110	100.00
Marital Status	Single	47	42.73
	Married	62	56.36
	Separate	1	0.91
	Total	110	100.00
Size of the family	2 Members	9	8.2

	3 Members	17	15.5
	4 members	48	43.6
	5 members and above	36	32.7
	Total	110	100
Area of location	Urban	73	66.4
	Semi – Urban	37	33.6
	Total	110	100

The above table shows that 66.4% are male and 33.6% are female. 29.1% are from the age group between 13-23 Years, 25.5% are from the age group between 24-35 years, 32.7% are from the age group between 36-46 years, 6.4% are from the age group between 47-55 years and 6.4% are more than 56 years of age. 1.8% have completed their SSLC/HSC level, 21.8% have completed their diploma, 71.8% have completed their post-graduation and 4.5% have completed their professional degree. 17.30% are students, 12.70% are from working class, 34.50% are professionals, 3.60% are house wife's 30% are business persons and 1.8% are retired persons. 26.4% are from joint family and 73.6% are from nuclear family. 42.7% are single, 56.36% are married and .91% are separated. 8.2% are having 2 members in their family, 15.5% are having 3 members in their family, 43.6% are having 4 members in their family and 32.7% of the respondents are having more than 5 members in their family. 66.4% are from urban area and 33.6% are from semi-urban area.

Descriptive Statistics:

Table 2: Inability to Control Craving

Particulars	N	Mean	SD
ICC1	110	3.47	.965
ICC2	110	3.40	1.015
ICC3	110	2.64	1.056
ICC4	110	2.31	1.020
ICC5	110	3.18	1.077
ICC6	110	3.06	1.086
ICC7	110	2.70	.973
ICC8	110	3.08	1.102

The above table depicts that the respondents agree towards their friends and family complaining towards using DG (Digital Gadgets) (3.47), spending too much time on DG (3.40), finding themselves engaged in DG for longer period of time than intended (3.18), trying to spend less time in DG and failed (3.06) and occupied on their DG when having compulsion to do other things which causes them problem.

Table 3: Feeling Anxious and Lost

Particulars	N	Mean	SD
FAL1	110	3.18	.979
FAL2	110	3.22	1.120
FAL3	110	3.33	1.033
FAL4	110	3.20	1.056
FAL5	110	3.61	.978
Valid N (list wise)	110		

The respondents agree towards becoming preoccupied with the thought of missing a call when out of range for some time, finding difficult to switch off their digital media (3.22), feeling anxious if not being checked for messages or switched on their digital media for some time (3.33), feeling lost without their digital media (3.20) and also agree towards their friends finding it hard to get in touch them if they don't have a DM.

Table 4: Mood Improvement

Particulars	N	Mean	SD
MI1	110	3.58	1.095
MI2	110	3.44	1.121
Valid N (list wise)	110		

The respondents agree towards using DM to talk to others when they are feeling lonely (3.58) and using digital media to make themselves feel better when they feel down (3.44)

Table 5: Comparison between gender and acceptance of respondents towards Subscale analysis of digital media addiction

Ho1: Gender has no relation towards Subscale analysis of digital media addiction

Particulars	Gender	N	Mean Rank	Chi-Square	Sig
Inability to Control Craving	Male	73	61.35	7.331	.007
	Female	37	43.96		
	Total	110			
Feeling anxious and lost	Male	73	58.71	2.226	.136
	Female	37	49.16		
	Total	110			
Mood improvement	Male	73	55.47	2.321	.000
	Female	37	55.55		
	Total	110			

Gender has a relation towards inability to control craving (.007) and acceptance of respondents towards DG leading to mood improvement (.000).

Table 6: Comparison between age and acceptance of respondents towards Subscale analysis of digital media addiction

Ho2: Age has a significant difference towards Subscale analysis of digital media addiction

Particulars	Age	N	Mean	SD	F	Sig
Inability to Control Craving	13-23 Years	32	3.07	0.5723	1.695	.007
	24-35 years	28	2.89	0.7174		
	36-46 Years	36	3.07	0.66302		
	47-55 Years	7	3.03	0.79736		
	Above 56 Years	7	2.41	0.79326		
	Total	110	2.983	0.67769		
Feeling anxious and lost	13-23 Years	32	3.30	0.59889	1.592	.012
	24-35 years	28	3.11	0.72302		
	36-46 Years	36	3.51	0.80491		
	47-55 Years	7	2.97	0.7868		
	Above 56 Years	7	3.37	0.7868		
	Total	110	3.30	0.73381		
Mood improvement	13-23 Years	32	3.71	0.98323	.972	.426
	24-35 years	28	3.53	0.8706		
	36-46 Years	36	3.43	1.08991		
	47-55 Years	7	3.35	0.55635		
	Above 56 Years	7	3.00	0.8165		
	Total	110	3.5091	0.96494		

Age don't have any difference towards Inability to Control Craving (.007) and feeling anxious and lost due to use of DG (.012) but age have a significant difference towards mood improvement due to use of DG.

Chart 2: Impact of subscale factors of digital media addiction towards digital distraction (DD)

When analyzing the dimensions taken for the research all the three dimensions taken for the study have equal contribution (inability to control craving (.33), Feeling anxious and lost (.33) and Mood improvement (.33) towards DD.

Findings:

- 66.4% of the respondents are male.
- 32.7% are from the age group between 36-46 Years.
- 71.8% are post graduates and maximum of the respondents are professionals (34.5%).
- 73.6% are from nuclear family.
- 56.3% of the respondents got married.
- 43.6% of the respondents have 4 members in their family.
- 66.4% are from urban area.

The respondents disagree towards hiding much time spent by them in DG from others and not having enough time to spend on DG. The respondents who are male have higher level of acceptance towards inability to control craving and meanwhile, female respondents have higher level of acceptance towards DG leading to mood improvement.

Inability to Control Craving:

The respondents from the age group between 13-23 years, 36-46 Years and from the age group between 47-55 Years agree and the respondents from the age group more than 56 years of age disagree towards inability to control craving.

Feeling Anxious and Lost:

The respondents from the age group between 13-23 years, 24-35 years, 36-46 Years and from the age group more than 56 years of age agree. Meanwhile, the respondents from the age group between 47-55 Years disagree towards feeling anxious and lost due to use of DG.

Suggestions:

The usage of digital gadgets has to be reduced by the public who are using it for a long period and who are using it due to influence of others as it creates a larger distraction which leads to lag in concentration of their regular work and also it may spoil their work which may lead to decrease in productivity in near future.

Conclusion:

The conclusion is that apart from the respondents who are from the age group between 47-55 the respondents from other age group felt anxious and lost due to use of digital gadgets and also female respondents believe that use of digital gadgets may lead to mood improvement. This factor has to be eradicated as this cause harm and may addict them towards continuous usage of digital gadgets in future period of time.

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